

Adaptive key generation algorithm based on software engineering methodology

Muayad Sadik Croock, Zahraa Abbas Hassan, Saja Dhyaa Khuder

Department of Computer Engineering, University of Technology, Iraq

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 23, 2020

Revised Jun 14, 2020

Accepted Jun 26, 2020

Keywords:

Key generation

Security

Self-checking process

SIGABA

Software engineering

ABSTRACT

Recently, the generation of security keys has been considered for guaranteeing the strongest of them in terms of randomness. In addition, the software engineering methodologies are adopted to ensure the mentioned goal is reached. In this paper, an adaptive key generation algorithm is proposed based on software engineering techniques. The adopted software engineering technique is self-checking process, used for detecting the fault in the underlying systems. This technique checks the generated security keys in terms of validity based on randomness factors. These factors include the results of National Institute of Standard Test (NIST) tests. In case the randomness factors are less than the accepted values, the key is regenerated until obtaining the valid one. It is important to note that the security keys are generated using shift register and SIGABA technique. The proposed algorithm is tested over different case studies and the results show the effective performance of it to produce well random generated keys.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](#) license.

Corresponding Author:

Muayad Sadik Croock,
Department of Compute Engineering,

University of Technology,
Al-sinaa Street, Baghdad, Iraq.

Email: Muayad.S.Croock@uotechnology.edu.iq, 120052@uotechnology.edu.iq,
120099@uotechnology.edu.iq

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last years, the searching for strong security keys that stand against the hacker key-breaking methods has been increased sharply. Thus, the introduced studies, methods and algorithms aimed to obtain these types of keys for using in security algorithms. This is to produce a security level sufficiently acts against the attacks and hackers. Different approaches have been adopted to generate the security keys with high variation in long, sub-sequence and correlations [1, 2]. At the other hand, software engineering methods have been combined with these approaches to increase the reliability of the generated security keys to resist the dominated attacks over numerous applications. One of these methods is the fault tolerance technique that is based on self-checking process to detect the happened faults [3-8]. The solution for the detected fault can be addressed throughout different ways depending on the utilized application.

Due to the importance of the security key management in the security research, many researchers have focused on proposing efficient algorithms. In [9], the authors provided a study on using software engineering for evaluating the security risks including identification system in humans using some image features that need software engineering for producing the reliable codes. In [10], a complete study for hardware security was introduced. This study included key points of using the techniques of software engineering in the key generation and management. Researchers of [11] considered the security of cloud computing in terms of authentication levels. The introduced method uses the software engineering in

managing the keys used in authentication, in which the security was guaranteed. In [12], secure keys were produced for cryptography methods to be used in network communication. This field had an important data to be transferred and this was the reason behind providing it. In [13], the cyber-physical systems had been secured using the investigated method based on software engineering technology. The presented system worked at the physical layer to adapt the hardware components within the system. In [14], different practical software engineering developments for security systems were introduced. The study provided a deep-thinking way to tackle the problems of security in developing the used software.

The authors of [15] introduced a dynamic mechanism for generating the required security keys. This mechanism was based on genetic algorithm in addition to the use of software engineering technology. Moreover, multiple key generation method was proposed in [16]. These keys were employed in combination with the actions of sharing and backup for data. In [17], ciphering method of DES was combined with generated keys for securing the storage of data in cloud. The keys were generated based on a proposed algorithm that depended on software engineering. The authors of [18] presented design and implementation of key generation used for image security. The image security utilized the generated keys in coding of included components. In [19], memory efficient based multi key generation method was proposed. This method has been employed for securing the sensitive data transfer over IoT technology in the cloud environment.

At the other side, the authors of [20] utilized the OFDM subcarrier response systems for transferring important data in secure way. The used security keys were generated in high randomness to ensure the strong of them. In [21], the key generation method for multilevel quantization was provided. In addition, the pre-processing was also secured using the same method. These keys were generated using software engineering techniques. The researchers of [22] used the genetic algorithm in designing the key generation method that could guarantee high randomness. The enhanced random keys were produced for symmetric ones.

It is well known that the researchers of [9-22] worked hard for producing high quality security methods based on random generated keys. In this paper, an adaptive random key generation algorithm is proposed. The proposed algorithm adopts the self-checking process in fault detection as a part of fault tolerance technique to produce high randomness keys. The NIST tests are considered as a success threshold for self-checking process. The generated keys should pass the allocated thresholds to be adopted as valid keys. The proposed algorithm is evaluated in terms of performance and the obtained results prove the claim of this paper.

2. PROPOSED SOFTWARE ENGINEERING BASED METHOD

As mentioned above, the proposed method is based on software engineering process to produce high quality random security keys. In order to ease the reading flow, this section is divided into the followings.

2.1. Structure of the proposed algorithm

Figure 1 shows the structure of the key generation algorithm. It is clearly explained that the data block firstly enters to the SIGABA approach. This approach is built using five main polynomial equations to increase the randomness in choosing the seeds for shift register. SIGABA was produced in World War 2 to encrypt the transmitted messages as shown in Figure 2 [23-24]. The selected polynomial by the SIGABA approach with 32-bit is passed to the least forwarded shift register (LFSR). The LFSR is responsible on generating the key with 128-bit length. Figure 3 shows the structure of the adopted LFSR.

Figure 1. Key generation algorithm structure

Figure 2. SIGABA device

At the other hand, Figure 6 illustrates the second case study, where the NIST frequency test is passed, while the serial test is failed. In this case, the generated key is considered as invalid and rejected. According to the proposed algorithm, the key is regenerated from again following the same steps. The regenerated key is passed both NIST tests as shown in Figure 7. In this case, the generated key is valid and ready to be used in the security methods.


```

C:\Users\CE-0038\Desktop\New folder\ConsoleApplication13 - finalfinal\Debug\ConsoleApplicati...
The following are the randome five equations:
10110001011011010011100100011010
01001010011111010111110110011110
10011110000111000110101110110001
11101000110001010111010001110100
1000110000010000111110110111011

The output of the SIGBA function which is a seed to LFSR:
00101111011100010101001010101011

the output of the LFSR:
00110100000110011010010010111100100011010010101000010010100101111101001010100010
1010000110110100110101010101010010100001110001011011
number of ones= 58
number of zeros= 70
frequency tests= 1.125
Frequency test is pass

number of ones= 58
number of zeros= 70
number of 00 = 30 number of 01 = 40 number of 10 = 39 number of 11 =
18
serial test= 8.72539
serial test is not pass

```

Figure 6. Invalid generated key case study


```

C:\Users\CE-0038\Desktop\New folder\ConsoleApplication13 - finalfinal\Debug\ConsoleApplicati...
the output of the LFSR:
00110100000110011010010010111100100011010010101000010010100101111101001010100010
10100001101101001101010101010010100001110001011011
number of ones= 58
number of zeros= 70
frequency tests= 1.125
Frequency test is pass

number of ones= 58
number of zeros= 70
number of 00 = 30 number of 01 = 40 number of 10 = 39 number of 11 =
18
serial test= 8.72539
serial test is not pass

The following are the randome five equations:
00110010011111001001110011010110
01111011100000001001110010110000
01011000000111000101010000110000
01001011001111101011100010011011
1110000100001011110100111111001

The output of the SIGBA function which is a seed to LFSR:
00100011100111001100100010000000

the output of the LFSR:
11001000100111110000010010001001011001101011011110100110010111101010010100011001
00000001011011000100100011101010011100101001010011101
number of ones= 60
number of zeros= 68
frequency tests= 0.5
Frequency test is pass

number of ones= 60
number of zeros= 68
number of 00 = 33 number of 01 = 35 number of 10 = 35 number of 11 =
24
serial test= 2.10629
serial test pass

```

Figure 7. Valid regenerated key case study

For more testing results, five examinations are performed for the proposed algorithm. The results of these examinations are shown Table 1. Table 2 explains the result analysis of all case studies including both NIST tests and the common couples of bits. All case studies are passed and produce valid keys, yet the case study number 5 is failed in the serial test. Thus, the proposed algorithm uses the software engineering based fault tolerance to regenerate the failed key. The regenerated key is also tested over the same NIST tests. The obtained regenerated key is shown in Table 3, while Table 4 lists the analysis of the new key and it will show that the key is passed both tests.

Table 1. Generated keys for different case studies

No	5 Polynomials as input to SIGBA (8 Bits)	32-bit output of SIGBA (8 Bits)	Generated keys (128 Bits)
1	011001001001010111111000010011 00100111111001011101101110101 011010010000011011000101000000 0111010001110001101010001111100 1010010000010111111111100010001	0000110110010110100111101 0010011	0001100101101110011000100100111 0111111011010011011101111001011 1110000010110001101101100010011 0111110000100001101001110001111 1001
2	10110000110100101000010011101010 1011111011000100110110101101110 001000100110101000011011000000 10111101110001100111100100011100 1101110010110110010110100110010	0000110100010100111111011 1110110	0101100011010100000100100011011 0001000111011000101100000010011 111101011001101111101101101000 1010110101111111000010001101001 1011
3	01011000111110101001001001111011 10110000101100011010010111000100 0111101100100101101101100000110 00011001110001010000001111011101 10011010100010010001100100001101	1100101110010100000100111 1000010	1001110001010111111010110001011 1111110011100001010111001010001 000000001011100001011001011101 000011101100101100011110000000 0010
4	01111100000011110100010111011100 01000111010101100111001010101000 11111101010011111010001100010101 011111001010111110110000011001 10001100111101001010010111001100	0011100100000001100111101 0110001	1101111111010001011000001110010 000011011101011111100110101011 0111100010011100000101111101000 1011110011110000010110100010101 0100
5	10110001011011010011100100011010 0100101001111101011110110011110 10011110000111000110101110110001 11101000110001010111010001110100 10001100000100001111110110111011	0010111101110001010100101 0101011	00110100000110011010010010111110 0100011010010101000010010100101 1111010010101000101010000110110 1001101010101001010000111000101 1011

Table 2. Results analysis for 5 case studies

No.	No. of zeros	No. of ones	No. of				Frequency Test	Serial Test
			00	01	10	11		
1	59	69	29	30	29	39	0.781=pass	1.447=pass
2	63	65	30	33	32	32	0.0312=pass	0.118=Pass
3	68	60	39	28	29	31	0.5=pass	1.854=pass
4	60	68	29	30	31	37	0.5=pass	0.720=Pass
5	70	58	30	40	39	18	1.125=pass	8.725=Not pass

Table 3. Regenerated key

No	5 Polynomials as input to SIGBA (8 Bits)	32-bit output of SIGBA (8 Bits)	Generated keys (128 Bits)
5	00110010011111001001110011010110 0111101110000001001110010110000 01011000000111000101010000110000 01001011001111101011100010011011 11100001000010111101001111111001	0010001110011100110010010001 0000000	110010001001111100000100100010010 110011010110111101001100101111010 100101000110010000000101101100010 01000111010100111001010011101

Table 4. Regenerated key analysis

No.	No. of zeros	No. of ones	No. of 00	No. of 01	No. of 10	No. of 11	Frequency Test	Serial Test
5	68	60	33	35	35	24	0.5 pass	2.10629 pass

4. CONCLUSION

An adaptive key generation algorithm based on software engineering process was proposed. This algorithm aimed to generate security keys of 128-bit with high randomness to ensure the accepted resilience against the attacks. The software engineering fault tolerance technique was used for checking the generated keys in terms of randomness based on NIST tests. These tests were employed as accepted threshold to be decided if the generated keys were valid or not. The proposed algorithm was tested over different case studies and the obtained results proved the validity of this algorithm in terms of generating reliable and random keys.

APPENDIX

Figure 4. Proposed algorithm

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Barker and A. Roginsky, "Recommendation for Cryptographic Key Generation," *NIST Publication*, 2019.
- [2] B. Buchanan, "The Hacker and the State: Cyber Attacks and the New Normal of Geopolitics," *Politics of Privacy & Surveillance*, 2020.
- [3] I. Sommerville, "Software engineering," *10th Edition, Pearson Education, Inc*, 2017.
- [4] R. J. Ellison, et al., "Evaluating and Mitigating Software Supply Chain Security Risks," *Research, Technology, and System Solutions (RTSS) and CERT Programs*, 2010.
- [5] M. Kuutilaa, et al., "Time Pressure in Software Engineering: A Systematic Review," *Elsiver*, 2020.
- [6] L. Mottola, et al., "Simplifying the Integration of Wireless Sensor Networks into Business Processes," *IEEE Transaction on Software Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 6, pp. 576-596, 2019.
- [7] Ayuba J., et al., "Software Development of Integrated Wireless Sensor Networks for RealTime Monitoring of Oil and Gas Flow Rate Metering Infrastructure," *Journal of Information Technology & Software Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1-10, 2018.
- [8] I. Almomani and A. Alromi, "Integrating Software Engineering Processes in the Development of Efficient Intrusion Detection Systems in Wireless Sensor Networks," *Journal of Semsors*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 1-28, 2020.
- [9] S. D. Khudhur and M. S. Croock, "Dental X-Ray Based Human Identification System for Forensic," *Engineering and Technology Journal*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 49-60, 2017.
- [10] Y. Jin, "Introduction to Hardware Security," *Journal of Electronics*, vol. 4, pp. 763-784, 2015.
- [11] S. Dey and S. D. Joshi, "ECC Based Authentication System for Performance Improvement in Security of Cloud," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 820-823, 2016.
- [12] Suresh H. and R. S. Hegadi, "DCA-SNC: Dual Cryptosystem Architecture for Secure Network Communication," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 198-205, 2017.
- [13] S. Ur Rehman and V. Gruhn, "An Effective Security Requirements Engineering Framework for Cyber-Physical Systems," *Technologies*, vol. 6, no. 65, pp. 1-20, 2018.
- [14] Safe Code, "Fundamental Practices for Secure Software," *Third Edition, SAFECODE*, 2018.
- [15] C. Chunka, et al., "An efficient mechanism to generate dynamic keys based on genetic algorithm," *Special Issue Article, Wiley*, pp. 1-10, 2018.
- [16] R. Hariharan, et al., "Multiple key Generation for Securing Data Sharing and Backup," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 166-169, 2019.
- [17] M. Tajammul and R. Parveen, "Key Generation Algorithm Coupled with DES for Securing Cloud Storage," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 1452-1458, 2019.
- [18] A. Sharma, et al., "Design and Implementation of key Generation Algorithm for Secure Image," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 5139-5146, 2019.
- [19] C. Thirumalai and H. Kar, "Memory Efficient Multi Key (MEMK) Generation Scheme for Secure Transportation of Sensitive Data over Cloud and IoT Devices," *International Conference on Innovations in Power and Advanced Computing Technologies*, pp. 1-6, 2017.
- [20] J. Zhang, et al., "Efficient Key Generation by Exploiting Randomness from Channel Responses of Individual OFDM Subcarriers," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 64, pp. 2578-2588, 2016.
- [21] M. Yuliana, et al., "A Simple Secret Key Generation by Using a Combination of Pre-Processing Method with a Multilevel Quantization," *Journal of Entropy*, vol. 21, no. 192, pp. 1-25, 2019.
- [22] A. Z. Zakaria, et al., "Enhancing the Randomness of Symmetric Key using Genetic Algorithm," *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 8S, pp. 327-330, 2019.
- [23] Level 1 Validation, "Sigaba Gateway FIPS 140-1 Non-Proprietary Security Policy," *Multi-chip standalone*, 2001.
- [24] H. E. Kwong, "Cryptanalysis of the Sigaba Cipher," San José State University, 2008.
- [25] M. Stamp and W. O. Chan, "SIGABA: Cryptanalysis of the Full Keyspace," San Jose State University, 2007.